

Demand-Side Energy Management Using an Economical Smart Energy Meter

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Abstract— The authors present a cost-effective universal smart energy meter (USEM) that supports both Prepaid and postpaid options that support different tariff structures like time-of-use rates, block rate tariffs, or a combination of the two. The smart meter incorporates a potential transformer, a current transformer, and a microcontroller with an integrated communication module. The connection between the utility provider, smart meter, and consumer is established via unique identification numbers for each entity, using a cellular network. Additionally, the smart meter includes demand-side load management features, allowing for control of electrical loads and the provision of emergency power during shortages. The meter can be remotely configured and reconfigured through SMS, without the need for hardware changes. Furthermore, the system monitors energy usage, detects meter tampering, and identifies faults on the distribution side. A prototype has been developed, demonstrating the system's practicality, adaptability, and multifunctionality through experimental validation.

Keywords— Universal Smart Energy Meter (USEM), Microcontroller, Integrated Communication Module.

I. INTRODUCTION

There is a growing demand for smart energy metering systems due to their ability to streamline revenue collection, enable remote monitoring, and manage power distribution effectively. Traditional electromechanical and electronic meters, lack advanced features of smart meters, leading to the introduction of automatic meter reading (AMR) systems, which combine communication infrastructure with electronic meters to facilitate remote data collection.. Although AMR reduces the need for manual meter readings, it requires a significant financial investment to set up the necessary communication infrastructure. Prepaid energy metering systems have gained popularity due to their efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and improved accountability they offer. However, challenges such as network connectivity, the limitations in interoperability, the constraints inherent in demand-side load management (DSLMM), and the difficulties in aligning with micro-generation systems have significantly attenuated the attractiveness of conventional metering solutions. Conversely, advanced metering infrastructure (AMI)-based systems, distinguished by their bi-directional communication capabilities, offer superior functionality and address these challenges with greater efficiency capabilities, offer enhanced functionality and address these limitations more effectively, and control devices, addresses many of the issues associated with older metering systems.

Notable features of AMI systems include DSLMM, remote tariff management, billing, fault detection, and tampering protection. The communication infrastructure is central to smart metering, and over the years, researchers have proposed various communication protocols such as Bluetooth, ZigBee, and power line carrier (PLC) communication, WiFi, and cellular networks. While PLC is cost-effective due to existing cabling infrastructure, it suffers from reliability issues, including interference and high signal loss. This work introduces a functionalities, effectively mitigates numerous limitations inherent in prior metering systems. Noteworthy contributions encompass the both hardware and software for configuring payment modes (prepaid and postpaid), implementing DSLMM, and facilitating remote tariff management. Additionally, the system integrates a comprehensive suite of monitoring and protective features, including voltage and overload protection, tampering notifications, recharging alerts, automatic reconnection capabilities, and power factor monitoring. Additionally, it offers mobile phone-based recharging and balance adjustment, making it a versatile and practical solution for modern energy management.

II. PROPOSED USEM SYSTEM

A. Complete system architecture

The proposed Universal Smart Energy Meter (USEM) system comprises three key terminals: the user end, meter end, and authority end. Each terminal is assigned a unique identifier for security and management purposes: The User Identification Authority Identification Number (AIN), Unit Identification Number (UIN), and Meter Identification Number (MIN). With complete remote access, the AIN is able to control and monitor any feature of the USEM. including demand-side load management (DSLMM), tariff plan configuration, switching between prepaid and postpaid payment modes, reconnections, and meter recharging center settings. The UIN allows the user to access basic meter information and remotely switch the meter on or off. After every operation, the MIN sends confirmation via SMS to either the AIN or UIN, depending on the action performed.

B. Metering architecture

The USEM's hardware architecture is intended to be less complicated and more affordable than that of conventional smart energy meters. Rather than utilizing costly energy measurement chips like the ADE 7751, a custom measurement circuit was developed using components such as current transformers (CT), potential transformers (PT), ADC ICs, a timer IC, and the ATmega2560 microcontroller. Unlike traditional voltage divider and shunt resistor circuits, which result in significant power losses, these components help minimize losses and keep costs low. The block diagram of single-phase Universal Smart Energy Meter (USEM) system illustrates the process by which Current Transformers (CTs) and Potential Transformers (PTs) convert the input current and voltage into manageable range. These converted signals are then processed through a amplified digital representations of voltage and current are subsequently transmitted to the ATmega2560 microprocessor.

The microprocessor performs temporal integration of voltage and current samples to calculate critical electrical parameters, including active power, reactive power, energy consumption, and power factor. This data is then displayed via an LCD driver, showing real-time energy consumption and power statistics. The ATmega2560 microcontroller, with its 86 I/O pins, allows for extensive control over the various functionalities of the USEM. The design incorporates two current transformers (CTs) for monitoring the main load, ensuring accurate measurements of both voltage and current. This simplified architecture not only lowers hardware costs, but also improves efficiency and accuracy of energy monitoring.

Fig. 1 Block diagram of single- phase USEM

To detect meter tampering, the USEM utilizes both the current from the load and feedback current. The phase wire and neutral wire are passed through the primary winding of a current transformer (CT). In this design, the CT model TA1309-200, with a maximum current rating of 5 A, is used. To extend its capacity, shunt wires of equal length and resistance are added. This ensures the CT can handle higher currents while maintaining accuracy. A real-time clock (RTC) is employed to store data in EEPROM at regular intervals, which aids in the creation of a flexible tariff plan. A power source selector is included to automatically switch to the battery during power cuts and back to the mains power when available.

C. Demand-side load management

By providing an emergency power source and efficient power utilization during a power outage, the integration of the DSLM system with the USEM helps lessen the impact load shedding has on customers. Water heaters, air conditioners, refrigerators, and water pumps are examples of high-power loads that can be directly controlled. The current study integrates the USEM with SMS-based remote controllable DSLM. Light load and heavy load are two categories of electrical loads at a consumer's premises that separated to allow for the remote load control system in the USEM. The Among the heavy loads are heaters, motors, refrigerators, microwaves, air conditioners, rice cookers, televisions, etc. emergency load (EL) is the light load, which is made up of fans and low-wattage bulbs. The user must designate their EL under a feeder, and the utility's server will retain the data. When there is a power outage computation is performed, and each The power is used to determine the consumer's EL that is available beneath the feeder at that particular moment. Every MIN receives SMS from the utility control room with the allowed EL limit, and the consumer receives the load limiting information via UIN. Fig. 2 displays the USEM DSLM algorithm. After receiving an SMS from AIN confirming the authenticated EL limit, USEM disconnects the relay connected to the heavy load and reconnects the consumer's approved EL.

The buzzer will beep to lower the ELs if the linked ELs exceed the consumer's allowed ELs. The automated system turns off the linked ELs after 30 seconds, and then it automatically turns on the EL relay to check the connected ELs again. The system operates normally with approved ELs if the connected ELs are less than or equal to the permitted ELs. If not, the buzzer beeps, and the mechanism again shuts down the linked ELs after 30 seconds. There are three iterations to the check-recheck procedure. The consumer receives information via UIN. Fig. 2 displays the USEM DSLM algorithm. Following receipt of an SMS from AIN confirming the authenticated EL limit, USEM disconnects the relay linked to heavy load and reconnects the consumer's authorized EL. All of consumer's loads will be permanently shut down if they do not modify their ELs within three attempts. After lowering the excess load in this case, the customer can use allowed EL by sending SMS to MIN. When power supply returns to normal, utility control room can send SMS to USEM to return EL limit status to normal. USEM can monitor a consumer's authorized loads (PLs) in the same way as ELs do. The maximum loads that a customer is typically allowed to utilize without incurring additional costs are known as peak loads, or PL's. When a user attempts to use more load than PLs, USEM will stop using all of the user's load and send SMS to the authority control room informing them of their situation so they may take appropriate action.

Fig. 2 Flow diagram of DSLM

D. Mode switching and flexible tariff setting

Every USEM function, including remote connection establishment and reconnection, payment method choice, and tariff plan setup, is controllable from either the authority or the customer end. Setting tariff plans and remote mode switching are two of the USEM's key features. Without modifying any hardware or software, the USEM can be configured in either postpaid or prepaid mode by just sending an SMS from an authority with a designated SMS code. It is also quite flexible, as well as flexibility in how tariff plans are formed (block rate, TOU, or both combined). From the utility control room, SMS configuration is available for all tariff levels. It should be mentioned that many third-world nations do not have a block rate and TOU tariff together. There are various approved SMS codes in USEM that can be used to set different tariff plans. Any value can be split up into three distinct plans using all tariff spans

E. Recharging system

The smart meter's flexible recharge technology adds convenience and is essential to DSLM. The current metering system's recharging is not flexible. Online credit card or online banking transactions were used for recharging. The primary constraint on this study is that not all consumers have access to online credit card and online banking systems. The USEM's recharging mechanism is easy to use, adaptable, and simple because it doesn't require a special vending station. Numerous current financial payment methods that are suitable for mobile recharging can be used to complete the recharging. Initially, the

customer uses his personal account, which is linked to his payment accounts such as credit card, cell balance, and online banking, to make a request via SMS to the utility server. Following a successful recharge, the utility server provides USEM with an authentication SMS, and the customer receives a confirmation SMS.

F. Bill calculation

Fig 3 shows the flow chart for the USEM recharging mechanism in both postpaid and prepaid modes. With the microcontroller, The suggested system allows negative balances within the authority-assigned date range. After the n th day of each month, the microcontroller verifies the current balance. It then uses a UIN to send the billing status to the user, along with the due date for bill payment. Following Before making a decision about the deadline, The microcontroller performs a redundant verification of current balance. Additional reconnection requires administrative approval, which comes with a cost. When using prepaid mode, the meter functions properly if the current balance is larger than XX (depending on the system utility authority); otherwise, system notifies the user through SMS to recharge balance The system functions normally if recharging is carried out; if not, the supply will be immediately disconnected after beyond the YY balance limit. Through recharging, the user can rejoin at any time.

Fig. 3 Flow chart of the USEM recharging system for prepaid and postpaid mode

G. Protection schema

There are protection plans available in USEM against the illegal use of energy, such as meter bypassing, disconnecting the neutral line, and tampering. Two CTs are used to compare phase current and neutral current in order to provide protection event. It is possible to identify partial bypass if the two measurements are not equal. When total bypassing occurs, PT in USEM monitors voltage and, should no voltage be detected at the PT, notifies AIN via SMS of the powerless condition. The authority takes appropriate action after verifying that the consumer can access the power supply. Light-dependent resistors are used in the optical detection technique to prevent meter manipulation. Additionally, when meter cover is opened, the connection between meter body and the cover is broken. This break may be readily identified by using the microcontroller's interrupt and ground pins. USEM disconnects the load and sends SMS to the authority to report any detected tampering. Additionally, in the event of an overload, undervoltage, or overvoltage, the USEM can safeguard the household appliances. There is constant monitoring of the voltage and current. The smart energy meter cuts off the customer's load and notifies the appropriate authorities and the customer if the voltage or current falls or rises above a predetermined threshold established by the utility.

H. Monitoring and Notification system

In addition to detecting overvoltage, overcurrent, and undervoltage, USEM also provides protection against these defects and alerts the appropriate authorities. A home is further protected by this kind of surveillance and security system. The utility server allows the authority to keep track of each customer's status, and SMS notifications are available for all relevant information, including billing details, payment deadlines, meter status, load shedding alerts, and device notifications.

Fig. 4 Implemented USEM device

III. PERFORMANCE OF USEM

Universal Smart Energy Meter (USEM), as illustrated in Figure 4, provides critical data including power factor, system voltage, energy consumption, connected load, and remaining balance. The USEM device represents a significant advancement in energy management technology, offering a comprehensive overview of electrical parameters essential for optimizing energy usage and ensuring efficient load management. Its accuracy was rigorously validated through a comparative analysis with the standard calibration meter, the Fluke 5502 A, Voltage measurements ranging from 150 to 300 V were compared, showing minimal error at 240 V, as depicted in Fig. 5a. Current measurements up to 15 A also exhibited minimal error, as shown in Fig. 5b.

The execution of key USEM Operations such as Mode transition, remote tariff plan configuration, recharge management, remote status surveillance, and tampering mitigation. The Authority Identification Number (AIN) and the Meter Identification Number (MIN) are the sources of these signal processes these commands, sending confirmation SMS messages after execution. The USEM alerts the authority in cases of meter tampering or violation of company rules, with detailed notifications sent to both the authority and the consumer. For demonstration purposes, the system currently uses SMS-based recharging and balance adjustments, without integrating a transactions. Temperature effects, frequency-dependent measurement accuracy.

Fig. 5 Measurement comparison with the USEM and standard calibration meter Fluke 5502A (a) Voltage, (b) Current

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